

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B487		
Date:	20 NOV 2009		
Take Off:	12:53:06Z	Z	Z
Landing:	15:03:03Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	2h 9m 57s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: QUEFA

Operating Area: Norwich Laps

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voaden	Directflight
4	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist	Jim Hopkins	Reading
6	Flight manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	WAS	Shalini Punjabi	York
10	CIMS	Max McGillen	Manchester Uni
11	CIMS	Michael Le Breton	Manchester Uni
12	Cloud Physics training	Angela Dean	FAAM
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
Y	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-11-05	Alan Woolley	Initial version
r1			
r2			

B487 10:31:54-15:04:25

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

asxx 20/11/2009 06:00 UTC

QUEFA sortie – B487

An around Norwich flight to quantify the emissions of Volatile organic compounds and other trace gases from the city.

WAS canisters should be filled in “fast-fill” mode. Given the relatively large number of WAS canisters on board we should aim to get an even spacing between samples (around one every 1 – 1.5 minutes) REGARDLESS of whether CO is calibrating.

Figure 1: Position of Waypoints during circuits around London and Norwich.

London sortie: F – A – B – C – D – E – F – A – B – C – D – E

Norwich sortie: G – H – I – J – K – L – G – H – I – J – K – L – G

Norwich sortie (approximately 2 hours)

#	approx time	approx altitude	detail
(1)	13:00	take off	Take off and ascend to FL100
(2)		10,000 ft	transit to operating area - <i>Fill some WAS canisters (5) at this level.</i>
(3)		descend	Descend into Norwich international airport and perform a missed approach
(4)		ascend	Ascend to 1300 ft. - <i>Or minimum safe altitude</i>
(5)		2300 ft	Perform two complete anti-clockwise circuits of the city at this level starting at point G (see figure 1). G - H - I - J - K - L - G - H - I - J - K - L - G. - <i>fill the remaining WAS canisters equally spread around both circuits approximately every 70 s.</i>
(6)		descend	Descend into Norwich international airport and perform a missed approach
(7)		ascend	Ascend to FL100 - <i>to verify the boundary layer height has not changed during the flight</i>
(8)		10,000 ft	Transit to Cranfield at FL100
(9)	15:00	landing	Land at Cranfield

EGTC -> EGSC - Overview

NavData Cycle 2009-12 Expires: Thursday, 17 December 2009.
Scale: 1:616750 (1 inch = 8.46 naut mi). Printed on 19 Nov 2009

76996 ; 68

FliteStar 9.4.7.0

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B487

Date: 20/11/09

Project:QUEFA

Location:Norwich

Start	End			
Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg Comments
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124409		taxy	0.41 kft	000 start
124441		asp open	0.40 kft	055
125306		T/O	0.40 kft	211
131215	132446	Profile 1	11.0 - 0.21 kft	068
133002	135319	Run 1	1.4 - 1.1 kft	215
133548		ovhd H	1.4 kft	182
133838		ovhd I	1.2 kft	115
134140		ovhd J	1.1 kft	359
134450		abeam k	1.1 kft	300
134911		abeam L	1.1 kft	294
135319	141652	Run 2	1.1 kft	246
135922		ovhd H	1.1 kft	179
140224		ovhd I	1.1 kft	087
140417		ovhd J	1.1 kft	058
140738		ovhd K	1.1 kft	002
141223		ovhd L	1.1 kft	296
142645	143011	Profile 2	2.0 - 0.21 kft	263
145117		mpds failed	8.6 kft	234 stowed video laptop?
145422		mpds back	3.7 kft	224
150303		Land	0.33 kft	212 cranfield

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 29 NOV 09

Flight No: B487

Pre-Flighter: JC

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	✓	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	CHEM OPERATOR
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4		Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	CHEM OPERATOR
5		Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	"
6	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	✓	HORACE	Recording data	B487
10	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	✓	Nevezorov	Checked and OFF	NEV TWC u/s
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	x	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	NOT FITTED
17	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	✓	Satcom C	Checked	
23	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	x	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT FITTED
25	x	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
26	x	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	NOT OPERATED
27	x	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	NOT OPERATED
28	x	3876 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	NOT FITTED

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	✓	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	NET FITTED
30	✓	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	"
31	✓	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	"
32	✓	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	"
33	✓	3786 CPC	Drained	"
34	✓	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	"
<u>External Checks</u>				
35	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	Nevezorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
43	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
44	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
45	✓	All other covers	Removed	
46	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
47	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
48	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	
49				
50				
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
51		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
52		ICEX applied		
53		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B487
Date: 20 Nov 09

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC still u/s despite vane change. Suspect box/wiring.
- 2.

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Cloud Physics Flight Log B487

Date:	Operator:	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	AUX1 Time:	AUX2 Time:
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20/11/2009

Angela Dean

DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2		FFSSP	
Operated?												
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.2	Vref (>7V):	7.8	El#1 V (>1):	2.13	El#1 V (>1):	2.8	Comms?:	Y	Vref (>3V)	3.1
	Data TX?	y	Sample flow	1.17	El#32 V (>1):	3.27	El#32 V (>1):	3.6				
			Sheath flow	13.9	El#64 V (>1)	1.72	El#64 V (>1)	2.7				
			Spectra ok?	y								

Zeroed 11:40

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?		Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?			

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
												CDP: 8 micron – 11:47:50 – 11:48:30 (approx)
												CDP: 40 micron – 11:53:00 – 11:54:00 (approx)
												PCAS P – 12:41:50 spike in PCASP 28V current corresponding with pink error message on screen. "VISA read in SPP200 get data.vi>spp200 9.vi "
												CDP turned on 12:44.
												All heaters switched on 12:55.
												CIP 15 – images only on LHS of screen.
												Lwc configured for FL110 13.01
												Lwc configured for FL130 time ???
												LWC configured for FL100 14:36
												All heaters off before landing.

Flight B487 – Complete vIRC chat log

